

THE WAYS OF FORMATION THE INTEREST FOR COGNITION IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10157089>

Abstract. *This article reveals in detail the content and the main directions of organizing the formation of primary school students for knowledge, while the types of relationships between subjects and objects of the educational process are highlighted. The phenomena that develop student activity and his abilities, types, forms, means, methods, methods and techniques that contribute to improving the interaction of participants in the educational cycle. The effectiveness of the unity of emotional perception, theoretical thinking and practical activity of students is revealed.*

Keywords: *interaction, experiment, observation, object, cognition, activity, assimilation, development, method, description, didactics.*

The activities of students who are subjects of the educational process, aimed at mastering educational actions, are called educational activities. Students will have the opportunity to develop independently and gain knowledge in the process of solving educational problems. The teacher, in this process, sets special tasks for students that are based on external control and assessment, and thanks to this, students acquire self-control and self-assessment skills. Justifying the importance of educational activities in the mental development of students, D.B. Elkonin highly appreciated its place in the development of cognitive activity. Purposefulness, independence, and self-control are manifested in the process of forming younger schoolchildren as subjects of activity; their mental characteristics and behavior change. These changes are due to the individual efforts of students. Students are characterized by knowledge, skills and competencies that ensure the activity of their actions as subjects of the process of mastering new knowledge.

Educational activity in the process of primary education is a complex didactic event due to its characteristic features. It includes educational directions, content of educational tasks, educational activities, control and assessment situations.

Students' learning activities take place within certain types of interaction. In this process, students strive to solve learning problems together. At the same time, they will have the opportunity to apply the acquired knowledge, skills and competencies. The involvement of teachers and students in the process of joint research is based on the mutual sharing of joint activities.

The developmental nature of educational activity is directly related to its content, methods of its organization and the nature of joint activities of subjects of the educational process. The teacher must regularly take care of the scientific content of educational activities, the ease of students' assimilation of scientific concepts and the methods of their assimilation.

Intellectual actions, verbal means, the content of academic subjects, new knowledge that needs to be learned, and personal experience of students are the main means of students' educational activities.

Tools that allow students to become subjects of the learning process focus on enhancing their cognitive activity. The formation of interest in knowledge and the development of students' cognitive activity makes it possible to organize educational cooperation. This is manifested in the following: 1) influence on the development of students, their learning skills, group formation through joint activities; 2) didactic justification for their influence on the formation of new types of activities in students and independent study of joint actions.

Collaboration occurs in the unity of time and space as a process of joint activity, an organizational system of students' cognitive activity, and a form of didactic communication. The main areas of cooperation in educational activities are manifested at the level of teacher-student-students, student-students, group cooperation of students. The following levels of educational dialogues that accelerate the cognitive activity of students are distinguished:

- "teacher – student";
- "teacher – students";
- "student – book";
- "student - educational materials" and so on.

In addition to the above types of dialogue, internal dialogue is also important for ensuring students' cognitive activity.

The principles of teacher-student cooperation not only guarantee the transfer of new knowledge to students, but also contribute to their personal development, dialogue in the learning process, the creation of problematic situations in the process, individualization of students taking into account their specific characteristics, humane communication, and allows for the creation of a positive pedagogical and psychological environment.

In the process of joint learning, mental problems are successfully solved and communication skills are quickly formed. Purposeful views on mental activity, based on control and evaluation, are formed, and analytical abilities are developed. Working in groups accelerates students' learning activities by directing them towards a specific goal. This, in turn, allows them to develop cognitive activity. Allows students to plan activities from outside based on the distribution of roles. As a result, they successfully learn to work together.

A number of studies have different views on the composition of student groups. It is indicated that groups consist of two, three and several students. The influence of communication on the implementation of thought processes is directly related to many factors. These include the characteristics of the students involved in the collaborative process, the interrelationship of the strategies adopted by them, the methods and means of communication, and the relationship between teacher, student, and students.

The analysis process reflects various aspects of the mutual distribution of students' activities. The joint activity, modeled by the teacher and presented to the students, made it possible to substantiate two directions for organizing joint learning activities. It should be noted that there are also psychological ways to control these actions. One of the characteristic features of the first direction is the clear transmission of activity techniques that teachers present to students in the form of models and drawings. The organization of the activity process in the second direction indicates the possibility of restructuring the activities of students with the help of the teacher. In

this case, the teacher uses a collective approach. This process will radically change the way students interact and collaborate with the teacher. In this way, a link is established between joint action and problem-solving methods.

In the primary grades, the main educational activities are carried out within the first direction. Work in the second direction was organized after the students' cognitive activity was activated.

A joint search for the essence of future activity, a joint determination of its goals makes it possible to determine the content of interaction. In this process, the participants themselves determine the nature of communication. In the process of communication, students not only exchange ideas about certain things and events, but also share their views and feelings about these things and events. The process of developing students' speech is directly related to the study of material existence. The study of material existence allows students to develop their inner speech and thinking.

The formation of listening skills is also of particular importance for the development of students' cognitive activity. At the same time, it is extremely important to learn how to correctly formulate thoughts. In this case, the ability to compare information in different texts devoted to the problem is formed. In this way, students differentiate between their common and different aspects. Comparing different pieces of information helps students understand the essence of the information. Students will be able to identify the main idea of a text using comprehension skills. They perceive the content of the text based on the posing of various questions and answers to them.

Of particular value is the implementation of physiological directions for enhancing the cognitive activity of students. This, in turn, serves to ensure the physical activity of students. Brief physical activity during classes with elementary school students is extremely important to keep them active. The results of the study show that finger movement is the basis of brain activity. The results of a study of hand movements and the movement of small muscles in it showed that such exercises can ensure the functioning of brain activity in 7-year-old children.

Providing students with adequate physical activity allows them to work in class without distractions and focus on the topic of study. In addition, it provides a basis for ensuring their speech activity.

The process of organizing students' cognitive activity shows that each subject taught in an educational institution has its own characteristics.

Social situations must be included in the learning process to activate students' cognitive activity. This approach allows you to organize the learning process taking into account the social experience of students. In this process, objective existence is embodied in the eyes of students with all its contradictions and variations. In this process, with the help of the teacher, students understand the essence of reality and form their own idea of it.

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